

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**COMPARISON OF VARIOUS TRANSFORMATIONS IN FACE
RECOGNITION TECHNIQUE**¹B.Kiran Bala and ²R.Meena

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, K.Ramakrishnan College of Engineering, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India., ²Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, K.Ramakrishnan College of Engineering, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India.

Article Received: April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Powerful technique in the present technology is face recognition to get attention of all over the world has been made and to strengthen that technique this system made to extract the feature and make the comparison among the Discrete wavelet transformation, Wavelet transformation and fast Fourier transformations are taken for the comparison to extract the best transformation to process the system and we are going to take two important aspect like false acceptance rate and false rejection rate will be taken into the account for the entire process and we have taken own as database.

Keywords: Fast Fourier Transformation, Discrete wavelet Transformation, Wavelet Transformation, Face recognition.

Corresponding author:**B.Kiran Bala,**

Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
K.Ramakrishnan College of Engineering, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India.

Email: kiranit2010@gmail.com.

QR code

Please cite this article in press B.Kiran Bala et al., *Comparison of Various Transformations in Face Recognition Technique.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

The system will be sharply pointed on the various transformations like fast fourier transformation, discrete wavelet transformation, wavelet transformations to extract the effective and efficient

transformation to give best result to strengthen the face recognition technique and the proposed diagram shows the entire and from the own database we have taken the images for the process [1-3].

Figure 1. Basic Architecture Diagram of the system

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

In the figure2 shows about the feature extraction methods and comparison of the transformation through the FAR & FRR justify the result and own database used for the entire process [5-7]. The edge

detection in the face recognition for the proposed system sobel used for the process and result of the sobel will be given input to the transformation and finally made the result.

Figure 3. Edge detection output

Figure 2. Selection of Best Transformation

Implementation:

The entire system used own database from that totally 101 images used for the proposed system and feature extracted like edge and then used those

transformation to identify the best transformation to find out the best one we are using FAR and FRR to find out the efficient transformation among those transformation [4-7].

Table 1. Comparison of Transformation

S.No	Transformations	FAR (%)	FRR (%)
1.	Fast Fourier	98.12	97.03
2.	Discrete wavelet	99.01	98.12
3.	Wavelet	98.12	97.03

CONCLUSION:

The Entire system process the various transformation like Fast Fourier, Discrete wavelet and Wavelet transformation from that process the edge detected image to the transformation totally 101 images taken from that FAR, FRR has been consider for the effective detection of transformation of the face recognition algorithm for the better results.

REFERENCES:

1. Kiran Bala B, Audithan S, 'Wavelet And Curvelet Analysis For The Classification Of Microcalcification Using Mammogram Images', Publisher: IEEE, ISBN: 978-1-4799-7986-8, Page: 517-521.
2. Kiran Bala B, Lourdu Joanna J, 'Multi Modal Biometrics Using Cryptographic Algorithm', European Journal of Academic essays, ISSN: 2183 1904, vol 1 Issue 1, February 2014.
3. Kiran Bala B, Nithya T.M, 'Remedy For Disease Affected Iris In Iris Recognition', International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology, November Issue 2012, ISSN: 2319 – 1163, page No. 332-334.
4. Kiran Bala B, 'A Novel Approach To Identify The Micro Calcification Images', Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences , JCHPS Special Issue 2: February 2017, Page 190-192.
5. Kiran Bala B, Audithan S, Kannan G, Raja, K, 'Frequency Domain Approaches For Breast Cancer Diagnosis', Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences, Vol. 10, No. 2, pp. 93-96, 2016.
6. Kiran Bala B, 'A Novel Approach To Generate A Key For Cryptographic Algorithm', Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences , JCHPS Special Issue 2: February 2017, Page 229-231.
7. Kiran Bala B, Audithan S, 'Comparison of Different Transforms For Earlier detection of Breast Cancer by Using Mammogram Images', International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, Vol. 13, No. 8, pp. 6411-6413, 2018.